

Buddhist Arts of Konedawgyi Temple

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Abstract

Konedawgyi Temple (Temple No-151) is situated in the east of Nyaung U, south of That-kyamuni, Temple coordinates N: 51.300 E: 13.615. It is a kind of medium sized single storey temple and lies at the centre of an enclosure wall with one gate each on north and south. It consists of square central shrine, entrance hall on east side with porch and lateral porches, vestibule and porch on south and north faces. The interior decoration of Bagan temples consisted of wall paintings. It covered almost entirely the ceiling vaults and all of the interior walls. Painted designs were performed as a framework of architectural moldings. Konedawgyi temple has full of paintings depicting Buddha life stories, as far as we can study this temple was the best and completeness on the subject on Buddha life stories, and we can see original paintings of late 12th century AD Bagan Period. Thus, this temple has full of historical importance for scholars and researchers.

Introduction

Konedawgyi Temple (Temple No-151) is situated at the hill top, in the east of Nyaung U, south of That-kyamuni Temple, not far away from Chauk Baya Hlagyi Temple and Chauk Baya Hlange Temple, coordinates N: 51.300 and E: 13.615. It is a kind of medium sized single storey temple and lies at the centre of an enclosure wall with one gate on each north and south.¹ It consists of square central shrine, entrance hall on east side with porch and lateral porches, Vestibule and porch on south and north faces.² At the exterior of temple, stucco moldings were found such as ornate cornice and pediments, friezes with pointed obovals. The interior decoration of Bagan temples consisted of wall paintings. It covered almost entirely the ceiling vaults and all of the interior walls. Painted designs were performed as a framework of architectural moldings. There are two internal staircases in east corners of entrance hall, and small aperture on west forepart. This temple is constructed by brick masonry; average brick has 37 x 16 x 4 cm. Over the square central shrine, there are the three square terraces: the first square terrace with one projection and corner stupas, the second terrace with two projections, axial niche and corner stupas, the third terrace with two projections and axial niche. Over the three terraces, the circular bell shaped dome, and conical spire were also found.³ Cloister vault was used over the central shrine. Barrel vault hipped at east end over entrance hall and barrel vault over vestibules and porches were also found. There were also used stone pavement and reinforcements. Stone was commonly used to strengthen brick work, especially at corners and in arches. Stone bricks were set at intervals within brick courses.⁴ In central shrine, one renovated Buddha seated facing East, against a screen wall.⁵ Since the early Bagan period to late Bagan period, outer walls of stupa, temple, monastery, etc (sasana) religious buildings were decorated by using stucco as architectural ornaments. At the exterior of Konedawgyi temple, stucco moldings were found such as conical spire, plinth, corner pillar of kalakyaung, dado, cornice, arch pediments, back slab, corner pediment and bell were decorated with ornate cornice and pediments, friezes with pointed obovals. Belu panswe, inverted lotus petal, fully bloomed lotus petals, row of bosses, crenellated parapet, floral designs, frieze with ogre heads,

¹ Fig. 1, Konedawgyi Temple (or) Temple No-151, from South, Pterre Pichard, Inventory of Monuments at Pagan, KISCADALE EFEO UNESCO, Volume 1, 240

² Fig. 2, site plan of Konedawgyi

³ Fig. 3, south face, from South west

⁴ Fig. 4, corner stone brick

⁵ Fig. 5, vestibule and renovated Buddha

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kitimukha frieze, tasseled frieze with pointed ovals, tassel, base with recess, mythical birds keinara, lion, makara and horse were also found.⁶

The Konedawgyi temple faces to the east and it has one devotion or shrine hall and three porches. Above the porch or entrance gate of Konedawgyi temples, the back-slab or back rest with arch pediments and fine beautiful stucco arts can be seen they were decorated with floral designs, motive of mythical birds, makara, serpent, and other animals such as lion, horses, human being and fish, etc.⁷

Therefore, Konedawgyi temple was well known for outer wall stucco carving and inner Buddhist mural paintings. Konedawgyi temple has full of paintings depicting Buddha life stories. Mural paintings of the Bagan temples were created and worshipped systematically, Jataka stories were drawn around the corridors of the temples in strict sense and the paintings were drawn according to the size of the temple; the subjects were Jataka and Buddha birth stories. Bagan temples and Pahtos were built from ninth Century to thirteenth Century. Bagan period was embellished with floral designs based on floral arabesque method has symmetrically use of lines and it has a soft and stylish manner, the artists do not use lines or other kinds of stuff to create the floral designs; instead he used his own imagination, so that the art works were his own idea or creation.

Paintings of taking preordainment of events made by Buddha were found in the south porch, west wall of Konedawgyi Temple. The paintings can be found at the south porch, west wall and the paintings show the subject matter of taking preordainment of events made by Buddha. In one of the previous lives Gotama Buddha was a lion king and he took preordainment from Paduma Buddha, Paduma Buddha was residing and sat in Dharmachakra mudra at the seven storey monastery with his two disciples; the face of Buddha was akin to Myanmar—the artist drew the face of the Buddha in tranquility mood, two eyes were cast down, lips smiling, ears not fallen down to the shoulder. According to the painting it can be assumed that this temple was built in the late 12th century AD or early 13th Century A.D. To the left of the temple a lion figure was in standing posture and took preordainment from Paduma Buddha, the lion's face was painted in a humble mood, showing no pride, horrific, cruelty, roaring and in angry posture. Instead the lion was paying obeisance to the Buddha in humble manner. The artist had drawn this subject in detail.⁸

Under the painting we can read the words in ink glosses “as a young man Uttara takes preordainment from lord? Sumedha Buddha”.⁹

In one previous life Gotama Buddha was born as a young rich person, Uttara and he took preordainment from Lord Sumedha Buddha. Young rich man Uttara believed in Sumedha Buddha teachings and donated all his personal properties saving under the earth to the Sumedha Buddha and disciple monks— his personal properties were billions in number and

⁶ Fig. 6, Back slab and corner pediment, from East face, east forepart; Fig. 7, lion on the Orge head from East face, east forepart; Fig. 8, mythical bird keinara descends to makaras mouth and lotus floral from corner pediment (from East face, east forepart); Fig. 9, Hourse, birds and lotus floral, Ogre (kitimukha head from back slab of West Porch, from North West; Fig. 10, Stucco art from North forepart; Fig. 11, figures of Makara, man and bird, Sri Gods and lotus floral, from North forepart; Fig. 12, man and Sri God; Fig. 13, lion, man and Sri God and lotus floral, Stucco art from back slab of North forepart; Fig. 14, lotus floral, from North forepart; Fig. 15, Stucco from South forepart; Fig. 16, Ogre head, Lion, Sri God, Makara, mythical bird, Kinari, hintha and Arch pediments from back slab of South forepart

⁷ Fig. 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16

⁸ Fig. 21, lion king and Paduma Buddha; Fig. 22, ink glosses (Field work)

⁹ Fig. 23, young rich man Uttara and Buddha, with ink glosses (Field work)

Sumedha Buddha preordinated after thirty thousands of eons became Buddha. Though some portions of the painting were ruined we can trace by ink glosses.¹⁰

The scene depicts that the young person Uttara takes preordination from Sumedha Buddha. Under the painting we can read the ink glosses as “Donations ceremony has lasted for seven days”.¹¹

It shows the ceremony of Sumedha donation. There was an ink inscription “When Bodhisattva recluse to the forest Depankara Buddha resides at the monastery named Thudasana”,¹² and the painting also expressed on the subject Depankara Buddha was residing at Thudasana monastery when Sumedha recluse to the forest. Under the painting the words such as “Sumedha recluse to the forest, King of celestial beings and Setkya-min figure (Sekjawadei:min, sovereign of the four islands of the universe)” were inscribed.¹³

We can see the paintings on Bodhisattva Sumedha recluse to the forest and reside at the monastery created by King of celestial beings, Dipankara Buddha becomes Buddha and resides at Thudasana monastery, when he walked through to the city with begging bowl for food, other people made a path (or) route for Buddha, the road had been made clean without any obstacle but there was a muddy spot on the route, the ground was also wet in this spot. Sumedhaa sage could not do anything in that movement. So he lay down on his stomach in that spot and made a request to the Buddha to step over his back and cross the muddy spot on the road. Thumeda sage lie down on the muddy road as a bridge for Dipankara Buddha and his disciples to cross over his shoulder, when Buddha and disciples were disappeared Sumedha sage considered his acquired virtue on the muddy road.¹⁴

Paintings in the north porch west side of central shrine has full of Buddha’s life stories. Big painting was put in the center, small paintings were encircling around the big painting in twelve parts. In these small paintings there were life stories of Gotama Bodhisattva, he takes preordination from Sikhi,¹⁵ Vessabhu¹⁶, Kakusandha¹⁷, Konagamana, Kaunagon, and Kassapa Buddha’s by giving meritorious deeds.

These paintings were taking preordination scene from north porch of west side of Konedaw Gyi temple. Bodhisattva king Sudassana giving robe to the Vessabhu Buddha and takes preordination.¹⁸ Vessabhu Buddha becomes Buddha under the Sal tree, Lord Buddha resides at five storey monastery with two disciples. Bodhisattva Sudassana is sitting on the ground and pouring water symbolically after his meritorious deeds.¹⁹ Sudassana wore a smock-light garment on his body, the garment was ornamented by a circular shape of lattice of fences and floral designs were put at the center of circle. He also wears a crested headdress (a magai) on his head and artist drew beard on his chin. Artist created the joyful face of a Sudassana after he accomplished his meritorious deeds. This painting may be regarded as a 12th Century

¹⁰ Fig. 24, ink glosses; Fig. 25, ink glosses

¹¹ Fig. 25A , The ceremony of Sumedha donation

¹² Fig. 26, Depankara Buddha was residing at Sudassana monastery

¹³ Fig. 27, Depankara Buddha was residing at Sudassana monastery

¹⁴ Fig. 28, Sumedha sage lie down on the muddy road as a bridge for Dipankara Buddha;

Fig. 29, Ink glosses ဤကားဘုရားလောင်းတောထွက်သောဒီပင်္ကရာပုဂ္ဂိုလ်သိင်္ဃသုဒ္ဓါနမည်သောကျောင်း နေ၏။

Fig. 30, ink glosses ဤကားပုဂ္ဂိုလ်သိင်္ဃဒီပင်္ကရာသွားစေဌာလူများဘံ(တံတား)ပြု၏။

Fig. 31, Ink glosses

Fig. 32, Sumedha sage ဤကားဘုရား အလောင်းညွန့်မှ ထေရ် အလှူပါရမီကို ကြည့်အံ့ဟု ပန်းပုံထက်ဝယ်နေ၏။

¹⁵ Fig. 33, preordination from Thiki

¹⁶ Fig. 34, king Sudassana and Vessabhu Buddha; Fig. 35, king Sudassana

¹⁷ Fig. 36, king Khema and Kakusandha; Fig. 37, king Khema

¹⁸ Fig. 34, king Sudassana and Vessabhu Buddha

¹⁹ Fig. 35, king Sudassana

painting which expressed the King of Bagan dressing style and manner and the painting depicts the subject on Bodhisattva Gotama. In this time he was known as King Sudassana and he made meritorious deeds such as giving robes and other offerings to the Lord Vessabhu and Arahats; Lord Vessabhu gave preordination to king Sudassana that in future (13 eons from that time) the king may be reincarnated as Lord Buddha. This was written in ink glosses as follows: “Bodhisattva King Khema donated robe and offerings to Lord Kakusandha Buddha and took preordination”,²⁰ Kakusandha Buddha resided at five storey monastery with his two disciple monks; Kakusandha Buddha was sitting in Dharmachakra mudra, Kukusandha Buddha became Buddha under a kind of tree, kou kou (Albizzi lebbck). When Kakusandha Buddha attained Buddha-hood Bodhisattva Gotama was king Khema. King Khema donated robes and alm bowls to Kakusandha Buddha and his disciples, he preached Kakusandha Buddha teachings and became novice monk also. Then Kakusandha Buddha gave preordination to king Khema. In the painting Khema sits in kneeling posture, pouring the water on the ground, while he wears magai headdress and long robe also. His robe is ornamented by floral designs.²¹

It was also written in ink glosses as follows “Pissaka offering in gold loungji to Lord Konagamana and takes preordination”. Gotama Buddha was a king named as Pissaka at the period of Lord Konagamana, the king offered Lord Buddha and his disciples with silk and white fabulous robes and gold foot wear and took preordination, Konagamana Buddha became Buddha hood under the water fig tree, kneeling down on the ground and clasping his two hands and paid homage to Lord Buddha.

Ink glosses were written under the painting as follows, “Then He becomes king Weithandra he gives his sons to Zuzaka Ponna”. The painting expressed about king Weithandra giving his wife and sons to Zuzaka Ponna(Brahman), One can see king Weithandra pouring water , his queen sitting behind king Weithandara fulfils her husband meritorious deeds, Zuzaka accepts the offerings, two children kneel down on the ground and bowing respectfully to their father, paintings on elephants, horses and chariots were drawn in frame also.²² In his last life as human being he became as King Weithandra who donated his wealth, wife, daughter and son, and then he passed away.²³ After death he existed in Tuthita celestial plane,²⁴ and Bodhisattva Gotama Buddha mother’s dreams of a white elephant entering in her womb,²⁵ and Maya gets pregnant and the birth of Bodhisattva sequences were drawn in the painting. There were ink glosses written as follows, “Bodhisattva's mother queen Maya was placed at comfortable bed in the Himalaya by four celestial beings (nats), Queen Maya dreamt that she was carried by four celestial four beings to Himalaya”.²⁶ Queen Maya took percepts and slept in the bed celestial beings entered her chamber and took her away to the Anawwata lake,²⁷ and adorn her with made dress and her sleep at the gold palace facing towards east direction. Under the painting the words are written by ink gloss as follows, “This was auspicious Ingyin tree, under that tree Bodhisattva mother Maya met four celestial beings”.²⁸ In the present condition what was left inside the picture is Maya and her sister and on the sky, figures of two beings one Bodhisattva, two Brahmans and Ingyin tree can be seen. The other potions were the scenes were mostly damaged. Painting expressed about birth of Bodhisattva, Maya and her sister Godami who wore thin, silk sarong see through and, two ladies were

²⁰ Fig. 36, King Khema and Kakusandha Buddha

²¹ Fig. 37, King Khema

²² Fig. 38, Donation of King Weithandra

²³ Fig. 39, King Weithandra dead

²⁴ Fig. 40, King Weithandra, he gives donation in his life and then After dead he existed in the Tuthita

²⁵ Fig. 42, Maya sleeping at Himalaya; Fig. 41, Queen Maya dream

²⁶ Fig. 41, Queen Maya dream

²⁷ Fig. 43, Anawwata lake and Queen Maya dream

²⁸ Fig. 41, Queen Maya dream

standing in Tribinga posture. As Maya had lost energy her legs were quivering and she held tightly to Gawdami shoulder, Gawdami feet were gripping the earth to hold Maya body.²⁹ Two Brahmans kneeling down on the ground, holding Bodhisattva with gold pot and other nat flying in the sky, he hold gold pot in his hand and pours water to Bodhisattva; it was painted in detail.³⁰ Artist wishes to the viewers two Brahmans warmly accepted Bodhisattva,³¹ He painted three Bahaman heads. Under the painting words were written by ink glosses follows, “The idea was to express nats trying to made Bodhisattva's mother sleep in her bed, Bodhisattva becomes elephant in Maya’s womb”, this was a Maya’s dream sequence. The painting expressed about Maya sleeping at Himalaya, white elephant entered to her womb, nats used their power to sleep Maya in the Himalaya, and nats and forest guardian angels were kneeling down on the ground paying respect to Bodhisattva; Bodhisattva created as white elephant and enters to her mother’s womb, but we can find elephant’s tail only. Other parts were damaged.³²

Dream sequence of bathed by nat. Paintings about five rivers flows from Anawwata lake, birth of creatures such as elephants, horses, buffalos and cows. There is no Maya figure in this painting but we can see Anawwata Lake and nats having bathed Maya in the lake in the painting so that we can say it was drawn to depict Maya dream.

Under the painting is written by ink inscription as follows, “As King Waithandra Bodhisattva gives enormous donation and he existed at Tuthita celestial plane after death”. The painting depicts on King Waithandra, who gives donation in his life and then after death he existed in the Tuthita nat plane.³³

Under the painting words were written in ink gloss as follows, “Bodhisattva was a young prince name in Kassapa Buddha and he ordained monkhood and takes preordination”. This painting refers as Bodhisattva named was Jitipala and ordained monkhood in Kassapa Buddha time.³⁴

At the north porch and east side of the central shrine there was a huge painting, twelve small parts or small paintings based on Buddha Life stories were encircling the huge painting, in the small parts there were paintings on the subject of birth of Lord Buddha; Brahmans and nats carrying the Lord Buddha and relaying one after another, and he very much enjoyed his life as a prince in the palace.³⁵ Under each paintings words were written by ink gloss on the subject of the paintings, out of twelve there were only seven can be seen, three were damaged and two paintings were difficult to study because of the color were already faded out. In the huge painting we can see Lord Buddha was residing in the monastery and sitting with Bhumisparsha mudra, on the right of the Lord Buddha Brahma was standing in closing the umbrella posture and on the left King of Celestial beings standing and holding a conch shell in his hand; twelve small paintings were encircling the huge painting.

When Lord Buddha was born the child was received by human beings, nats and Brahmans and three paintings illustrated about this subject, and under the paintings one can find the words such as “Bodhisattva has been taken by nats from Brahma hand and four nats received with timber skin”. There was a painting on four celestial nats received Bodhisattva from Brahmans with black timber skin, “This Bodhisattva has been received by human beings

²⁹ Fig. 44, birth of Bodhisattva and Maya)

³⁰ Fig. 45, nat flying in the sky and pours water to Bodhisattva;

³¹ Fig. 46, Brahmans warmly accepted Bodhisattva

³² Fig. 42, Maya sleeping at Himalaya; Fig. 43, Anawwata lake and Maya dream

³³ Fig. 39, King Weithandra dead; Fig. 40, King Weithandra, he gives donation in his life and then after dead he existed in the Tuthita.

³⁴ Fig. 47, Jitipala and Kassapa Buddha

³⁵ Fig. 48, Bodhisattva has been taken by nats from Brahma hand and four nats received with timber skin

from the nats by Pwat Phu”.³⁶ Human beings received Bodhisattva from four celestial nats with valuable Bywe Phu. Under the painting words were written by ink gloss such as follows, “Bodhisattva descends from human beings and walks out seven steps on the ground”. There was illustration on the subject on Lord Buddha descends from human beings hands and walks out seven steps and he declared I am the first, highest and noble in the whole world, and there were paintings about Brahmas (three heads seen in the painting) holding umbrella to cover Lord Buddha from sun rays and Thuyama nats holding birds fans in their hands stands on the ground, one nat hold water pot in his hand and Ingyin flowers were blossoming paintings can be seen.³⁷ Another painting lower parts was damaged only these lines can be read– Sages were worshipping, some water color drawings has only the lines; and in that we can seen the figures of King Thudawdana holding his son Siddhattha in his arms and shows Siddhattha to Dewila sage, Siddhattha feet were stepping on the head of Dewila sage.³⁸ Dewila sage tight his hair in two pieces, the sage smiles heartily because he knows that Lord Buddha was born in this world; and all human beings may be freed from sufferings if they learnt and practice Buddhist doctrines, thus the sage staring Buddha's face and pay homage to Buddha clasping his two hands– the artist draws the painting in grand manner.

There was a painting illustrated on the birth of Buddha and five days later five Brahmins palmists and astrologers pay visit to the court and they read the child's future with their knowledge. There were no ink glosses under that painting; we can read the lines “Palmists read Bodhisattva hand” only. King Thudawdana who was residing in the palace chamber held Bodhisattva in his arms, the child shows his foot to the sages and two sages were kneeling down on the ground and studying the lines on the foot; five sages were sitting on the ground and them also prophesying the child's future at all.³⁹ There was another painting illustrated the subject in summer Bodhisattva residing at the grand mansion with nine storey accompanied by court ladies. In this painting it is written in ink describing, “In hot summer days Bodhisattva resides at his palace with forty thousand court maidens” lines were written with ink glosses. Another painting illustrated Prince Siddhattha resides at his palace with forty thousand maidens in winter season at the seven storeys court mansion. Under the painting ink glosses describes the subject as follows, “This picture was about in winter Bodhisattva resides at his palace and take with forty thousand court maidens”.

At the corridor walls of shrine and chamber hall there were paintings which were continued from east side of north porch. At the north east entrance gate wall paintings comprises with the Bodhisattva, and at the north wall there were paintings about Prince Siddhartha playing in the garden, seeing the vision of four persons the aged, the sick, the dead and the recluse, and at the south wall paintings about Siddhartha recluses to the forest and becomes enlightened one. Konedawgyi temple also called Konetawgyi temple has full of paintings depicts Buddha live stories, as far as we can study this temple was the best and completeness on the subject on Buddha's live stories, and we can see original paintings of Bagan. Thus this temple has full of historical importance for scholars and researchers. These paintings can be seen at north wall of the entrance gate of central shrine, under the painting the words were written by ink inscriptions as follows, “Bodhisattva saw the monks and like him”.⁴⁰

³⁶ Fig. 49, Human beings received Bodhisattva from four celestial nats with valuable Bywe Phu

³⁷ Fig. 50, Lord Buddha descends from human beings hands and walks out seven steps

³⁸ Fig. 51, Siddhartha and Dewila sage

³⁹ Fig. 52, Palmists and Siddhartha

⁴⁰ Fig. 56, ink gloss ဤကာပုဂ္ဂိုလ်လောင်းဥယျာဉ်ကစာတံအံ့သောရဟန်းမြင်ရကာနစ်ခတံ၏။

There was a painting on Bodhisattva paid visit to the garden every four months, in the garden he met the monk created by celestial nats from Tuthita plane and Bodhisattva believes on monks and then he wants to become a monk also.

According to Zinathtapakathani, Bodhisattva was riding on the four Theindaw horses, the chariot was decorated with jewels and he went to the garden, but in the painting the chariot was drawn by two horses only, and the chariot has two wheels instead of four wheels chariot, the artist drew the figure he saw in the real life of, Bagan; the artist drawn Waizayannar chariot (Weizajan chariot) with artistic imagination and it can be said the chariot was the best, the most beautiful in Bagan at that time.⁴¹ After seeing the monk Bodhisattva was residing on the rock bed king of the celestial being send his follower Withakyon nat, the nat came in front of the Bodhisattva in low profile and put nat dresses on Bodhisattva body. In the paintings figures about Bodhisattva wearing nat dresses and sitting on the rock bed, King of celestial nats and Withakyon praying Bodhisattva, on the sky flying sky nats holding lotus buds in their hands and those flying sky nats were held by different kinds of birds; the paintings were wonderful,⁴² under the painting ink glosses can be seen and there were words on “Withakyon nat dresses on Bodhisattva body”.

And the paintings about Bodhisattva ascends to the palace and slept, musicians and dancers playing,⁴³ Bodhisattva returns back from the garden he can not sleep well so that musicians and dancers tries to console his grief, under the painting ink inscription written as follows, “Not to takes recluse musicians and dancers console him”.⁴⁴

After midnight Bodhisattva awoke and studied the women dancers and musicians, he distasted them and prepared to recluse to the forest, under the painting ink gloss describes as follows, “Bodhisattva dislikes upon the female dancers and recluse to the forest.”⁴⁵

These paintings can be seen at south side of the entrance gate of central shrine. Paintings consists of Bodhisattva take along his companion Hsanda, Khanaka horse and take recluse to the forest, Hsanda clasping his hand and follows behind his master Bodhisattva, when the horse gallop his feet will tramp to the ground and sound of the horse footsteps will awaken the city dwellers so that two nats holding horse feet with their hands not to make sounds, when Bodhisattva arrived the city gate he met evil nat from Thawuhhti told Bodhisattva not to take recluse, if Bodhisattva abandon his idea he can reign as a king within the four big islands surrounded by 2000 islands within seven days.⁴⁶ Under the painting ink inscriptions on “Evil nat prohibited not to take recluse, nats prevent not to make out of noises of horse footsteps.”⁴⁷

In Zinathtapakathani kyam when the horses tramping on the ground four nats take horse foot not to make noises, but in the painting there were two nats only, Hsanda holds horse tail and one nat holding an umbrella to make shelter for Bodhisattva.

“Nats make fireworks, Brahmans, Galone and dragons pay homage to recluse Bodhisattva”, the painting depicts on nats taking part in Bodhisattva taking recluse to the

⁴¹ Fig. 53, Waizayan chariot

⁴² Fig. 54, Bodhisattva and Withakyon nat

⁴³ Fig. 55, Bodhisattva, musicians and dancers

⁴⁴ Fig. 58, ink glosses ဤကာဘုရာလောင်းတောထွက်စေရာ ကခြေစည်သူမ်(သည်) ဖကြီးရုံစေယျ။

⁴⁵ Fig. 59, Bodhisattva and Dancers

⁴⁶ Fig. 60, Bodhisattva and evil nat (mar nat) .

⁴⁷ Fig. 62, ဤကာဘုရာလောင်းတောထွက်မာနတ်တာမြစ်၏။ မြင်ခွာသံမဟိစေရာနတ်တို့ဖန်၏။ Evil nat prohibited not to take recluse, nats prevent no noises of horse footsteps

forest. Mar nat prohibited Bodhisattva not to take recluse but nats provided not to make horse noises, words were written in ink inscriptions, pictorial Zinathtapakathani kyam wrote as follows; “nats put their hands under the horse shoes not to make noises”, although in the painting it described as only two nats put their hands under the horse shoes, and Hsanda touching the horse tail in praying posture, we can see one nat holding umbrella to protect Bodhisattva from sun rays. This painting describes about nats follow behind Bodhisattva taking recluse to the forest and they hold thousands of torches, some nats holding uncountable torches and fireworks; these fireworks turned into floral buds and fallen down to the earth as rain of flowers and some nats playing music with musical instruments, this scene describes auspicious ceremony on Bodhisattva taking recluse to the forest. In the painting nats not only follow behind Bodhisattva but also Dragons and Galone-Garuda (Mythical birds) take part in that ceremony at all,⁴⁸ but there was different figure can be seen; Hsanda doesn't hold horse shoes instead he holds umbrella and covering Bodhisattva body. Under the painting ink inscription words were written as follows, “Nats play fireworks, dragon and Galone pray”.⁴⁹

Kanaka took Bodhisattva and Hsanda and crossed Anawmar river, when Bodhisattva reached the other side of the river bank he makes resolution; if he will becomes true Buddha his hair may be fly upwards to the sky and never fell down onto the ground. Thus he cuts off his hair with his sword; he threw up into the sky. The king of celestial being catches the hair with jewel ornamented floral basket. The painting depicts this event. We can see Bodhisattva cutting his hair, king of celestial receiving with circular tray,⁵⁰ Hsanda praying Bodhisattva in kneeling posture and Kanaka stands on the ground and watching towards Bodhisattva; under the painting ink inscription written as follows, “Bodhisattva crossed Anawmar river, cuts hair and king of celestial nat received Bodhisattva's hair”.⁵¹

The painting depicts about the subject on Under Kasapa Buddha Gahtikara Brahman, the friend of Kasapa donated eight articles for use by Buddha monks and lotus robes to the Kasapa Buddha; Bodhisattva resides on the throne, Brahman offering lotus robe but we can see Bodhisattva body and Brahman head only, full postures may be damaged.⁵²

Under the painting ink inscription written as follows, “this was Bodhisattva”. When he set a foot on the other side of Anawmar River Kanaka horse passed away and Hsanda left away; the horse dead at the place Bodhisattva can not be seen, the artist wants to portray this event wrote ink inscription under the painting.⁵³

At the vault of East face entrance gate there was a painting on lotus buds with 16 petals, at the meeting points of four lotus buds we can find quarter foil shape floral designs and at the centre of 11 petals there was circular design, in the centre of the circle Buddha sitting on Dharmachakra posture which was drawn in lotus stamen 9. In the 11 floral petals four nats holding lotus flower in their hands and flying on the sky were circling the Buddha's image; each nats were divided by three lotus leaves and in the centre of the flowers ogres with tooth were drawn in different pattern. Four nats are referred to Catulawkaparla nats. In the quarter foil of the circular design there were heads of four ogres, those four ogres heads were put on the four lotus buds which was encircled by Buddha image, Lawkaparla nat and four directions

⁴⁸ Fig. 61 , Bodhisattva taking recluse to the forest

⁴⁹ Fig. 63, ink gloss, Nats makes fireworks, Brahmans, Galone and dragons pay homage to recluse Bodhisattva”

⁵⁰ Fig. 64, Bodhisattva cutting his hair, king of celestial receiving with circular tray.

⁵¹ Fig. 64, king of celestial nat catch the hair

⁵² Fig. 65, Bodhisattva and Brahman

⁵³ Fig. 68, The horse dead at the place Bodhisattva can't seen.

and four ogres encircling the huge lotus from four directions, thus this may be reference to Mandala painting.⁵⁴

At the east face entrance gate of central shrine upper vault south side frieze has two pointed tasseled frieze, the paintings on figure and floral was different, in the two circular shape floral designs lions were crouching but the face to opposite direction, on the circular shape floral design Kanarar with magai on his head was flying in the sky and above that creature lady ogre stepping her foot on the kanara body figures can be seen. In the pointed frieze has two circular shape floral designs and in the circular floral design there was Hamsa bird (Brahmani Duck),⁵⁵ Under the frieze there was a painting about the subjects on Mar nat obstructed Bodhisattva not to take recluse, nats conveyed Bodhisattva, Bodhisattva cuts his hair, Brahmans offers lotus robe and dead of Kanaka horse sequences were drawn also. At the east face entrance gate of central shrine upper vault north side has lack of frieze, under the blank frieze there was paintings on Bodhisattva pay visit to garden and met the monk, under the command of king of celestial plane Withakyon nat making ornamentations, musicians plays music and Bodhisattva dislike upon the female dancers and made decision to recluse to the forest. At the south part of the vault there was Buddha live stories paintings, under the painting there was figure of Avalokiteshvara and at the both side of east face entrance gate Bodhisattva stands in Wara mudra- loving kindness posture.⁵⁶ Bodhisattva left hands holds lotus leaves and in the lotus floral designs no dead birds resting and on the right side floral designs small sparrow like birds were resting. At the other side of the north side of the vault Meitreya Buddha figure was drawn in the time of temple building. Mahayanists firmly believes that Avalokiteshvara governing the world between Demised of Gaudama Buddha and the birth of Arinmeitreya Buddha; Avalokiteshvara was a savior, protector and the most loving kindness master for human beings; he has many existences and different names such as Shiva or Mahathera, Vishnu and in female form Kali goddess, Kwan Yin and Tara Devi. At the west of central shrine and west of lateral porch there were figures on four nat Bodhisattvas paintings between floral reliefs.⁵⁷

Two nats holding lotus flower in their hands and sits at the foot of the cave, those two nats were cloud messenger nats, the Bodhisattva holds lotus flower in his hand wears insignia of honor on his shoulder diagonally and the ogres uplifting the nats on the sky.⁵⁸

Vault from north lateral porch at the west side of the central shrine ceiling consists of two monkeys sit in facing each other and two spotted owls spreading their wings and sitting on one of the other, two lions embracing each other, two elephants, two deer's, two brown pigeons and two white pigeons, two ducks, two buffaloes, two doves entwining each other, (they were in happy mood in lovely manner), two tigers entwining each other, an elephant tries to kill a lying tiger with his teeth, two cows embracing each other, a man riding on the bird's shoulder and two parrots entwining each other figures were drawn in the circular shape frame, and another circular frame encircle the former one; and in the latter circular shape lotus flower figure was drawn with black color, the back ground was hue color. In the floral lotus relief snakes were drawn as floral design, in the circle we can seen painted figure on a small bird and squirrel were facing each other; it was an amazing painting.⁵⁹

⁵⁴ Fig. 69, Mandala painting

⁵⁵ Fig. 71, circular shape floral design kanarar with magai

⁵⁶ Fig. 66, Bodhisattva stands in Wara mudra-loving kindness posture

⁵⁷ Fig. 72, Bodhisattvas paintings; Fig. 73, Bodhisattvas, lion and kanarar

⁵⁸ Fig. 74 and Fig. 75, Birds and the ogres uplifting the Bodhisattvas on the sky

⁵⁹ Fig. 75 and Fig. 77, ceiling painting of central shrine (painting of Vault from North lateral porch, west side)

At the east side of the vault from lateral porch there were painting about a monkey, squatting man, and two deer's embracing each other, a tiger was in standing posture, a bird with fox's head fly in the sky; those figures were put on the four feet creature with crocodile mouth, cow's head and cow's body.. On the nameless person head and body a strange creature biting flower in his mouth, a man riding the bird spreading his wings, a snake on the white cow, a man on the lion's back, a spotted owl, two dancing peacock were united in one unit as two heads and one body, a man with snakes on the deer and a man rides on the duck downtrodden the snake, a monkey encircled by snake on his body and a crane's head on the spotted owl figures were drawn on the circular shape design, and another circular design circling the former design; in the circular shape design there were snakes figures were drawn along with floral relief. On the walls from north and south of the vestibule there were Jataka and Buddha birth stories, Zataka tales paintings width and length was 4 x 4, Buddha Birth Stories width and length was 10.5 x 14 inches; and at the north wall of the vestibule there was a painting about Thuzata offering a milk to Lord Buddha- the enlightenment One was residing under the Banyan tree at Thena village at that time and Thuzata offering the gold cup full with milk as a meal, Buddha flows the gold cup in the river, dragon named Kala slept for many eons has waken up because of previous three Buddha's cups and the present Gautama Buddha's cup has been collided and the sound makes awake the sleeping Kala dragon and he prays the Buddha at once, Thawtiya the grass reaper offers eight piles of maps to the Buddha, Buddha lying peacefully on the ocean sequences were drawn in the paintings. Buddha attains Buddha hood and walks for 14 spaces and then he look backs to the Bodhi tree and throne, Praying Buddha tooth relics at Theinko city and Buddha preaching Dhamma to the sages, those subjects were painted in the north and south of the vestibule.

At the south of the vestibule there were paintings depict on the subject of Buddha preaching Dhamma to king Beinmathara, paying his hair to merchants Taphuttha and Balika, Preaching Dhamma to nats and Brahmins, having demises, descending from Tavaintha abode, preaching Dhammaceskra, conquering Narlagiri elephant, having recluse at Palaleya forest and birth of Buddha stories and events; all the paintings were drawn within the square frame. In the interior walls of Konedawgyi temple can be seen mural paintings and on the ceilings figures and floral designs of all kinds and on the walls we can see nats flying on the clouds.⁶⁰

Findings

Konedawgyi Temple has the original art works of stucco and paintings than other pagodas and temples in Nyaung U, especially Buddha Birth stories have been painted in the Temple. This Temple was built in late 12th Century Bagan period and the paintings represent the life of the people of Bagan and their Buddhism concepts.

Discussion

The interior decoration of Konedawgyi temple consisted of wall paintings. It covered almost entirely the ceiling vaults and all of the interior walls. Painted designs were performed as a framework of architectural moldings. Paintings of Konedawgyi temple was based on line drawing or one line drawing and drawn different figures in detail. The paintings show harmony, flexibility, mobility, calamity and sternly shapes and designs.

Base on lotus flowers and buds there were line drawings consists of natural scene; mountains, rivers as decorative designs. Starting from curve lines on floral pattern and then

⁶⁰ Fig. 79, ceiling painting of Vestibule

later birds, nats, ogres and other kinds of animal figures were existed in the paintings, line drawings of Bagan period was the most extraordinary of all the other line drawings of other periods and ages.

Conclusion

Most of the religious buildings in Bagan are related to Buddhist ideology. At Konedawgyi Temple, the Artists created paintings on Buddha's life stories, 28 Buddhas and taken recluse to the forest, Gotama Buddha took preordination from the 28 Buddhas, Gotama Buddha life stories, Gotama becomes Buddha hood and getting monsoon retreat for his entire life, Bodhisattva nats, Bodhisattvas, Brahmin nats and evil doers exist in the hell stories etc. The artists not only paintings but also describe the scenes in ink inscriptions under the paintings. Thus under the teachings of Buddhist philosophy Buddha sasana has been flourished in Bagan.

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Fig. 1. Konedawgyi Temple (or Temple No.151, from South

Fig. 2. Site plan of Konedawgyi

Fig. 3. South face, from South west

Fig. 4. Corner stone brick

Fig. 5. Vestibule and renovated Buddha

Fig. 6. Back slab and corner

Fig. 7. Lion on the Orge head from East face, east forepart

Fig. 8. Mythical bird keinar descends to makara,s mouth and Lotus floral from corner pediment (from East face, east forepart)

Fig. 9. Hourse, birds and lotus floral, Ogre (kitimukha) head from back slab of West Porch, from North West)

Fig. 10. Stucco art from North forepart)

Fig. 11. Figures (Makara, man and bird, Sri Gods and lotus floral, from North forepart)

Fig. 12. Man and Sri God

Fig. 13. Lion, man and Sri God and lotus floral, Stucco art from back slab of North forepart)

Fig. 14. Lotus floral, from North forepart

Fig. 15. Stucco from South forepart)

Fig. 16. Orge head, Lion, Sri God, Makara, mythical bird, Kinari, hintha and Arch pediments from back slab of South forepart

Fig. 17. Kitimukha

Fig. 18. Kitimukha ogre, top of the corner pillar (Frieze of deity and vegetation)

Fig. 19. Frieze with ogre

Fig. 20. Kitimukha ogre and lotus, from corner of plinth

Fig. 21. Lion king and Paduma Buddha (Field work)

Fig. 22. (inkglosses. ဤကားပဒုမဂုဏသွင်ထံတိုင်ပုဂ္ဂလောင် ခြင်သိယ့် ဖြစ်၍ ဗျာဒိတံခံ၏။)

Fig. 23. Young man Uttara, rich man and Sumedha Buddha with ink glosses

Fig. 24. Inkglosses (အလှူရက်ပေး၍ကုန်ရကစည်ကြီးလည်းပေး၏။)

Fig. 25. The ceremony of young man Uttara donation. (ဤကားသုမေပုရာ- ဣရလလင် ဖြစ်ဗျာဒိတ်ခံ၏။)

Fig. 26. Depankara Buddha was residing at Thudasana monastery

Fig. 27. Depankara Buddha was residing at Thudasana monastery

Fig. 28. Sumedha sage lie down on the muddy road as a bridge for Dipankara Buddha

Fig. 29. Ink glosses (ဤကားဘုရားလောင်းတောထွက်သောဒီပင်္ကရာပုဂ္ဂိုလ်တို့အားသုဒဿနမည်သောကျောင်းနေ၏။)

Fig. 30. Ink glosses (ဤ ကားပုရာသီခင်ဒီပင်္ကရာသွားစေဌာလူများဘံ (တံတား) ပြု၏။)

Fig. 31. Ink glosses (ဤ ကားဘုရားအလောင်းညွန့်မှထခ၍အလှူပါရမီကိုကြည့်အံ့ဟုနန်းပုံထက်ဝယ်နေ၏။)

Fig. 32. Sumedha sage

Fig. 33. Preordination from Sikhi

Fig. 34. King Sudassana and Vessabhu Buddha.

Fig. 35. King Sudassana

Fig. 36. King Khema and Kakusandha

Fig. 37. King Khema

Fig. 38. Donation of king Waithandra

Fig. 39. King Waithandra dead

Fig. 40. King Waithandra; he gives donation in his life and then After dead he existed in the Tuthita

Fig. 41. Queen Maya dream

Fig. 42. Maya sleeping at Himalaya

Fig. 43. Anawwata lake and Queen Maya dream

Fig. 44. Birth of Bodhisattva and Maya

Fig. 45. Nat flying in the sky and pours water to Bodhisattva

Fig. 46. Brahmins warmly accepted Bodhisattva

Fig. 47. Jotipala and Kassapa Buddha

Fig. 48. Nats received Bodhisattva

Fig. 49. Human beings received Bodhisattva

Fig. 50. Siddhattha walked out seven steps

Fig. 51. Siddhattha and Dewila sage

Fig. 52. Palmists and Siddhartha

Fig. 53. Waizayan chariot and Monk

Fig. 54. Bodhisattva and Withkyon nat

Fig. 55. Bodhisattva, musicians and dancers

Fig. 56. Ink gloss; ဤကာပုဂ္ဂလောင်ဥယဉ်ကစာတုံအံ့သောရဟန်းမြင်ရတာနစ်ခေတုံ၏။

Fig. 57. ink gloss; ပုဂ္ဂလောင်ဥယဉ်တွင်မင်္ဂလကျောက်ဖျာသုကြာ၊ ဝိသကြိတန်ဆာဆင်ပေ၏။
“Withakyon nat dress nat dresses on Bodhisattva body”.

Fig. 58. ink gloss; ဤကာဘုရလောင်တောမထွက်စေဂကခြေစည်သျှမ်(သည်) ဖကြီးရံစေယျ။
“Not to takes recluse musicians and dancers console him”.

Fig. 59. Bodhisattva and dancers

Fig. 60. Bodhisattva and evil nat

Fig. 61. Bodhisattva taking recluse to the forest

Fig. 62. Ink gloss; ဤကား ဘုရားလောင်းတောထွက်မာနတ်တာဖြစ်၏။ မြင်ခွာသံမဟိစေဂနတ်တို့ဖန်၏။
“Evil nat prohibited not to take recluse, nats prevent no noises of horse footsteps”.

Fig. 63. Ink gloss; ဤကာပုဂ္ဂလောင်တောထွက်သောနတ်တို့မီးရှူးထွန်းညှို့၊ ဗြဟ္မာ၊ ဂဠုန်၊ နဂါးပူဇော်၏။
Nats makes fireworks, Brahmans, Galone and dragons pay homage to recluse Bodhisattva”

Fig. 64. Bodhisattva cutting his hair, king of celestial receiving with circular tray

Fig. 65. Bodhisattva and Brahman

Fig. 66. Bodhisattva stands in Wara mudra- loving kindness posture

Fig. 67. Ink gloss; ဤကားပုဂ္ဂလောင်အနောမာနဒီမြစ်ခဲနိုက်၊ ဆံ--၏။ သိကြာကာဆံခဲ၏။
 “King of celestial nat catches the hair”.

Fig. 68. Ink gloss; ဤ ကာပုဂ္ဂလောင် စိသောကဏ္ဍကမြင်းပုဂ္ဂလောင်မျက်စိကွယ်
 “The horse dead at the place Bodhisattva can't see,

Fig. 69. Mandala painting

Fig. 70. Mandala painting

Fig. 71. Circular shape floral design and kanarar with magai

Fig. 72. Bodhisattvas paintings

Fig. 73. Bodhisattvas, lion and kanarar

Fig. 74. Birds and the ogres uplifting the Bodhisattvas on the sky.

Fig. 75. Birds and the ogres uplifting the Bodhisattvas on the sky

Fig. 76. Ceiling painting of central shrine
(Painting of Vault from north lateral porch, west side)

Fig. 77. Ceiling painting of central shrine

Fig. 78. Central shrine ceiling painting
(Painting of Vault from north lateral porch, west)

Fig. 79. Ceiling painting of Vestibule